

Effect of chemical treatments on some fungi that cause rice grain spotting.^a

Treatment	Concentration (ppm)	Fungus species growth ^b (ϕ cm)									
		<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	Unidentified	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Fusarium semitectum</i>					
Thiabendazole	0	2.74	de	3.80	d	2.01	c	4.83	c	4.85	a
	50	2.95	cd	3.20	e	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	100	2.92	cde	2.53	e	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	500	3.12	bcd	2.07	h	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	1000	2.84	cde	2.14	gh	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
Carbendazim	0	2.91	cde	5.77	ab	3.71	a	5.78	a	4.50	b
	50	3.57	a	5.89	a	0.97	ef	0.60	g	0.60	f
	100	3.60	a	5.72	b	0.73	fg	0.60	g	0.60	f
	500	3.50	ab	5.78	ab	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	1000	3.20	abc	5.85	ab	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
Mancozeb	0	2.49	e	4.69	c	2.85	b	5.65	b	4.49	b
	50	3.15	bcd	2.24	g	2.64	b	4.88	c	4.20	c
	100	2.78	cde	2.15	gh	2.81	b	4.68	d	4.52	b
	500	1.59	f	1.33	i	1.47	d	4.42	e	3.60	d
	1000	1.00	g	0.60	j	1.24	de	3.95	f	3.42	e

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.

1,000 ppm sterile distilled water. For each, 1 ml of the fungicide solution was mixed with glucose potato agar (GPA), melted at 50 °C, and poured in petri dishes. Agar slugs (6-mm-diam disks) of each species were then centered in the dishes containing the agar and fungicide concentrations.

Each concentration was replicated four times as was the control sample (0 ppm) in which 1 ml distilled water was added to the melted agar. Petri dishes were kept in an incubator at 25 °C. We measured colony diameters on days 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10.

A totally random design was used and a factor analysis of data was performed. Duncan's multiple range test was applied to evaluate the differences between mean values.

Of the three products, mancozeb had the greatest efficacy on *B. oryzae* and *C. lunata*, with the greatest effect at 500 ppm. Carbendazim and thiabendazole had good efficacy at 50 ppm in controlling the growth of *F. semitectum*, *F. moniliforme*, and the unidentified species. ■

Leafhopper transmission of the Philippine isolate of rice dwarf virus

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Rice dwarf virus (RDV) is a new viral disease of rice in the Philippines. It is presently found only in Midsayap, North Cotabato. Several leafhopper species are known vectors of the disease in countries where it occurs. We determined which leafhopper species transmit RDV in the Philippines.

Second-instar nymphs of *Nephotettix nigropictus*, *N. virescens*, and *Recilia*

dorsalis were allowed 4 d of access to RDV-infected Taichung Native 1 (TN1) plants. They were transferred to healthy TN1 seedlings for 4 d, and then, individually used to inoculate a 6-d-old TN1

Transmission of rice dwarf virus (RDV) by 3 species of leafhoppers.

Species	Insects tested (no.)	Insects that transmitted (no.)	Incubation period in vector (d)
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	400	40	8-23
<i>N. virescens</i>	400	0	-
<i>R. dorsalis</i>	400	0	-
Transovarial passage ^a			
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	579	60	0-2

^aInsects hatching from eggs of all female adults with access to RDV-infected plants.

seedling in a test tube. Until they died, insects were transferred daily to fresh seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and scored 1 mo after inoculation.

To test for transovarial passage of the virus, 2d- to 3d-instar nymphs of *N. nigropictus* were given access to a diseased plant for 4 d and then reared on healthy TN1 seedlings until they became adults. All female adults were selected and confined on healthy TN1 seedlings to lay eggs for 3 d. Nymphs that hatched were immediately tested for RDV transmission as above.

Among the three leafhopper species tested, only *N. nigropictus* transmitted RDV (see table). About 10% of those tested were active transmitters. The virus is persistent in the vector and has an incubation period of 8-23 d (av of 15 d). RDV was also passed through transovarial passage to the progenies of viruliferous insects. About 10% of the insects were congenitally infective. Eight percent of them transmitted RDV immediately after hatching.

RDV had an incubation period of about 9 d in the rice plant. The first sign of RDV infection was minute white specks on emerging leaves. Leaf symptoms became more conspicuous 3-4 wk after inoculation. Stunting on TN1 was very mild. Infected plants looked normal except for the white specks or streaks on leaf blades. Plants grown from seeds of infected plants did not show RDV symptoms.

Our results showed that *N. nigropictus* is the main vector of RDV in the Philippines and was not transmitted, as in other countries, by *N. virescens* and *R. dorsalis*. This difference in vector transmission may be due to either a difference in the colony of insects used or a difference in RDV strain. ■